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ABSTRACT. This study presents the results of infrared (IR) spectroscopy analysis of modified hide glue obtained by incorporating urea-formaldehyde resin into its composition. A comparative analysis of the IR spectra of unmodified and modified glue was carried out, revealing characteristic changes in absorption bands that indicate the formation of hydrogen and ion-dipole bonds between the collagen of the hide glue and the functional groups of the modifier. The studies showed that the modification improves the structural and physicochemical properties of the glue, as evidenced by shifts and changes in the intensity of spectral bands. A mechanism of chemical interaction between the components of the adhesive composition has been proposed. The resulting glue is characterized by stability, good solubility, and suitability for bonding leather products.

KEYWORDS: Leather, collagen, glue, urea, oligomer, urea-formaldehyde resin, hydration, IR spectroscopy.

I. Introduction.

Infrared (IR) spectroscopy is a method of optical spectral analysis based on the ability of substances to selectively interact with electromagnetic radiation by absorbing energy in the infrared region of the spectrum [1–6]. This method is suitable for the qualitative analysis of polymers, for example, to determine the composition of copolymers, the content of functional groups, the presence and content of foreign substances in the polymer, the degree of unsaturation, and more [7–11]. The IR spectroscopy method was used to identify the structure and determine the purity level of the substances [12–13].

In IR spectra, regardless of the aggregate state of the compound, each observed band is characterized by both frequency and intensity. The method of IR absorption spectra provides a reliable means to determine chemical interactions in compounds [14]. In this regard, the samples obtained were identified using the IR spectroscopy method [15–16].

II. Object and method of research:

A) Research object:

Hide Glue (GOST 3252). Hide glue is produced by boiling the hide trimmings, split trimmings, parchment offcuts, heads, paws, and scraps of raw hides and other collagen-rich sources with water, followed by concentrating the resulting solution and drying it. Hide glue is manufactured in slabs, crushed, and flake form. It is classified into five grades: extra, top, first, second, and third. The moisture content in the solid glue of all grades should not exceed 17%. The adhesive strength (in kgf/cm²) should be at least 100 for the “extra” grade; 75 for the top and first grades; and 60 for the second and third grades. The manufacturing methods for hide glue and bone glue are similar. The shelf life of hide glue is up to 2 days. Its resistance to mold is low. The glue is non-toxic [17].

Glue based on urea-aldehyde oligomers. This type of glue is mostly a condensate of urea with formaldehyde, which, upon curing, forms brittle, hard polymers that degrade in the presence of

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4

moisture and are prone to cracking and shrinkage. This type of glue hardens in the presence of oxalic, ortho-phosphoric, citric, and other acids. Depending on the type and amount of these additives, the glue can be cured in two hours to a day. Due to the instability of the properties of this type of glue and its low durability, wood flour, and starch are mandatorily added to its composition [18].

Table 1

Curing time of urea resins

Temperature, °C	Curing time of urea resins with 1% hardener "ammonium chloride"				
	MFS-1	MF-17	M-4	Umakol S	KS-11
20	24 h	8 h	6 h	10 min	1 h 10 min
30	5 h	5 h	3 h	6 min 22 s	30 min
40	1 h 30 min	1 h 30 min	1 h	2 min 36 s	11 min
50	30 min	45 min	25 min	1 min 45 s	4 min 50 s
60	13 min	25 min	15 мин 15 s	1 min 08 s	1 min 45 s
70	5 min 25 s	10 min 30 s	6 мин	58 s	1 min 42 s
80	2 min 55 s	5 min	3 мин	45 s	1 min 26 s
90	1 min 52 s	2 min 30 s	1 мин 30 s	39 s	1 min
100	60-65 s	1 min 20 s	45-60 s	31 s	45 s

Table 2 presents the bonding modes using urea resins.

Table 2

Bonding modes with urea resins KS-11

Mode elements	Warm	Hot
Substrate humidity, %	up to 6-10	6-10
Liquid glue consumption, g/m ²	110-150	110-150
Dry glue consumption, g/m ²	60-80	60-80
Press loading time, min	up to 3	1,5-2,0
Press temperature, °C	60-90	110-130
Specific pressure, kg/cm ²	5-10	8-12
Pressing time	5 min + 1 min for each mm of thickness of the glued part	4 min + 5 min for each mm of thickness of the glued part

In these studies, the urea-formaldehyde resin of grade KS-11, produced by the "Prom Smola" company in the Sergeli district of Tashkent, was used.

Б) Research methods:

Preparation of adhesive compositions. The adhesive compositions were prepared by mixing the studied components and additives in water. The modified hide glue represents homogeneous suspensions ranging from white to light brown in color, without foreign inclusions. They are fully miscible with water. During storage, an increase in viscosity norms of the modified hide glue is permissible [19]. The modified hide glue should be used no earlier than 24 hours after preparation. The composition does not require plasticization before dissolution; it dissolves easily in water with minimal time, energy, and effort.

Stability (shelf life) of modified hide glue. During storage, modified hide glue undergoes physicochemical changes, resulting in increased viscosity and changes in other parameters. Shelf life largely depends on the excess of the modifier in the glue and storage temperature. On average, the shelf life of modified hide glue is up to 6 months.

Viability of the glue. The viability of modified hide glue can be defined as the time during which the glue, after the addition of the modifier and other components, maintains its working viscosity (i.e., does not lose fluidity). The viability period ends when the liquid glue transitions into a gel-like product, which no longer possesses adhesion capability and becomes insoluble in water.

C) Methods of Physicochemical Research

IR-spectroscopic studies were conducted using a SHIMADZU UV-3600 spectrophotometer (Japan) in the wavelength range of 500–4000 cm^{-1} . The assignment of characteristic absorption bands was performed according to established methods [20–22].

II. Result and discussion

The regularity in the frequency change of C=O aldehyde valence vibrations under conjugation during phase transitions is similar. The valence vibrations of hydrogen attached to the carbonyl group of aldehydes appear around 2722.43 cm^{-1} , associated with composite frequencies involving C=O valence vibrations, serving as a reliable indicator of the CHO group in the urea-formaldehyde resin modifier within the hide glue.

These bands result from valence vibrations of the >C=O double bond. Since the carbonyl group is part of all starting aldehyde oligomers, complete absorption occurs precisely in this region.

From the obtained spectra, it is evident that the intensity of free carboxyl group vibrations significantly decreased, though the peak did not entirely disappear. This partial disappearance can be attributed to the –COOH groups reacting with aldehyde oligomers, with some remaining free and vibrating at the same frequency but less intensely.

Thus, in the spectra of modified hide glue, the intensity of absorption bands decreases slightly. Accordingly, IR spectra confirm the modifying and structuring effect of urea-formaldehyde resin on hide glue.

Structural-chemical, physicochemical, and spectral analyses confirm that the obtained modified hide glue with urea-formaldehyde resin is not a mechanical mixture.

Observation of hide glue revealed that the spectrum of hide glue produced via the new technology [23–24] has distinct peaks.

In all studied samples, a broad diffuse band is observed in the 3500–3000 cm^{-1} region, which is attributed to intra- and intermolecular hydrogen bonds.

The presence of strong intermolecular hydrogen bonds in the hide glue is observed around 2960.73 cm^{-1} .

Additionally, a saturated C–O bond is seen in the hide glue sample (Fig. 1) in the region of 1456.26 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 1. Infra-red absorption spectrum of the original unmodified hide glue

Broad bands in the 700–500 cm^{-1} range correspond to out-of-plane vibrations of =N–H groups in the collagen of hide glue. These characteristic spectral frequencies allow for the evaluation of a relative reduction in the number of =N–H groups compared to unmodified hide glue samples.

The absorption band for C=O and amide I valence vibrations occurs at 1645.25 cm^{-1} . It should be noted that hydrogen bond formation significantly affects this vibration, causing a frequency shift, especially during phase transitions.

In the region around 1386.82 cm^{-1} , vibrations of the saturated C–O bond are observed.

Broad out-of-plane vibrations of =N–H groups appear at 777.31, 729.09, 667.37, and 644.22 cm^{-1} .

The absorption frequency in the 3331.07 cm^{-1} region is associated with O–H group valence vibrations.

Fig. 2. Infra-red absorption spectrum of modified hide glue with urea-formaldehyde resin

In interpreting the modified hide glue spectra, strong intermolecular hydrogen bonds appear at 2960.73, 2873.94, and 2860.43 cm^{-1} .

Comparing the spectra, the broad diffuse band in unmodified glue between $3500\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ becomes narrower and weaker in the modified glue, indicating reduced intra- and intermolecular hydrogen bonding.

In the unmodified glue, the saturated C–H vibration at 1386.82 cm^{-1} shifts to 1408.14 cm^{-1} in the modified hide glue, indicating the formation of a $\text{CH}_2\text{--N=}$ group due to hydrogen bonding with the carbonyl group of the urea-formaldehyde resin.

Medium and broad bands in the $900\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region correspond to out-of-plane =N--H group vibrations. These characteristic frequencies allow for estimating the relative decrease in the number of =N--H groups in the modified hide glue samples.

The absorption band for C=O and amide I valence vibrations appears at 1635.64 cm^{-1} . As previously noted, hydrogen bonding significantly influences this vibration, causing frequency shifts, particularly during state changes.

As expected, a new absorption band appears at 1722.43 cm^{-1} in the modified glue that is absent in pure collagen, characteristic of C=C and C=O double bonds in carbonyl structures.

Based on existing literature and conducted studies, a mechanism is proposed for the reaction of collagen in hide glue with urea-formaldehyde resin (dimethylol urea). Figure 3 presents a probable reaction scheme between collagen in hide glue and urea-formaldehyde resin.

Fig. 3. Probable mechanism of the reaction of hide glue collagen with urea-formaldehyde resin (dimethylol urea)

Hydrogen bonding plays a crucial role in adhesion. This type of bond resembles electrostatic interaction and can form between unlinked groups within the same molecule, between molecules of the same substance, or between different compounds containing hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, or chlorine. Hydrogen bonding operates at distances up to $0.25\text{--}0.28\text{ nm}$. The hydrophilic nature of natural leather surfaces is attributed to hydrogen bonds formed between water molecules and hydroxyl groups of collagen in hide glue [2, 5, 25], as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig.4. Scheme of formation of hydrogen bonds between collagen of modified hide glue and hydration of the skin substrate surface.

When bonding natural polymers with synthetic adhesives, ion-dipole interactions occur. These bonds form between amino acid atoms and polar molecules containing C=O groups in urea-formaldehyde adhesives.

IV. Conclusion

Thus, it can be concluded that the interaction between the urea-formaldehyde resin introduced into the composition of hide glue and the collagen in hide glue leads to the formation of ionic bonds. These occur between the polypeptide, ionized hydroxyl, and amino groups of collagen and the active carbonyl groups of the resin. Alongside these, hydrogen bonds may also form between the urea-formaldehyde resin and the collagen of the hide glue.

The results of IR spectroscopic studies, which identify the types of chemical bonds, make it possible to determine the mechanism of interaction between collagen in hide glue and urea-formaldehyde resin. It was found that the primary interactions involve the formation of hydrogen bonds between the peptide groups of collagen on one side, and the carboxyl, and hydroxyl groups—along with the opening of the unsaturated double bond of the carbonyl group in the modifier—interacting with the amino group of the glue.

The synthesized emulsion-latex glue, obtained through the modification of hide glue with urea-formaldehyde resin, is easily soluble in water and acidic-alcohol solutions. It is intended for bonding less critical leather product components, and its basic physicochemical and mechanical properties have been studied.

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